

Reluctant to be Educational Leader

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ABSTRACT: Our study investigates the leaders' challenges looked at by current educational organizations. Universally, the requirement for top-notch academic administration has never been more noteworthy. However, developing proof recommends that hardly any academics are quick to lock-in. In this study, we explore scholastic educational leadership at the principal of a school from organizational and scholarly viewpoints. Our objectives are to explain early job academic approaches and positions towards scholastic educational leadership, what may lie behind these, and make proposals about how to support their future enthusiasm for scholastic educational leadership.

A privately respondent included, which was the principal of a school in Malaysia. The information was gathered from interview questions and utilizing meeting strategies dependent on semi-structured questions. Meeting information was dissected through a precise coding procedure to discover themes. In view of the examination of these topics, the most noteworthy subjects that developed reliably are hierarchical culture measurement, trailed by vision, strategic, authoritative objectives measurement, trailed by a common duty measurement, and the least is the element of reluctant leadership practices. The school vision, crucial, objectives were shared among individuals in the arranging and performance of exercises. Be that as it may, as a type of leader dependent on shared exercises, there are still spaces for improvements, for example, common belief, familiarity, and input of duties.

Overall, our small research gives clear to the developing collection of speculations and procedures researching advanced education culture. While the contextual analysis discoveries may not be generalizable, different organizations may profit by a portion of the bits of knowledge give.

KEYWORD: Headmaster, Leadership, Professional Work, Reluctant, Skill

I. INTRODUCTION

In the mid-twenty-first century instructive foundation overall faces an extensive leadership test. Our exploration investigates parts of the leadership challenges with an emphasis on understanding scholarly mentalities to the leadership. In choosing my title, I am recognizing that I am mindful that an entrenched view has risen in much leadership research, which recommends that through their perspectives and positions numerous scholastics exhibit vacillation towards influential positions. My title additionally indicates that I wish to explore, and conceivably challenge this view. Here I adjust my deduction to Bolden, Jones, Davis, and Gentle, (2015 p.05) who talk about the requirement to a look into that tries 'to expose regular fantasies and misguided judgments'. I trust that by seeing increasingly about scholastic mentalities and positions, and how they structure, this examination can possibly add to how establishments satisfy the need for the 'nonstop improvement' in leadership referenced previously. Scholarly ways to deal with expressions and social leadership have concentrated dominatingly on set up leader in the institutional setting (Goodwin2020). The adaptable and regularly problematic nature of the social worker place. Expressions of the human experience and social setting is a mechanical-biological system of numerous little activities that come up short on the HR foundation of increasingly corporate divisions. Execution is estimated through both budgetary and social measures, and the division traverses benefit and not-for-profit authoritative sorts (Petetskaya 2017).

The leadership is tricky and difficult to characterize the idea. In this article, we investigate the significance of leadership through the view of a gathering of center directors focused as potential leaders in the further instruction part. As of not long ago further training has been depicted as the dismissed 'center offspring' of English instruction: a near low status because of its specialized and professional ethos has brought about it being dominated by the approach needs of tutoring and advanced education. Qualities and view of inventive administration, perceiving that the alluring pioneer generalization is yet pervasive (Nisbett and Walmsley 2016).

As of late, there has been a recovery in scholarly surveys of leadership halfway on account of an equal enthusiasm among specialists. This specialist premium could have various reasons some of which may basically identify with the verifiable pattern of

crazes and forms and others that identify with the near disappointment of frameworks, markets, or smaller-scale electronic intercessions intended to convey on their guarantee to improve performance, profitability and polished skill in professional customer relations. Although leadership is a challenging idea, this paper adopts a social constructionist strategy, contending people build leadership through activity, language, and administration talk (Crevani 2015). Late expressions the officials study about has recognized that hopeful leaders don't really esteem the advancement of leadership abilities, liking to depend on specialized skill, and inborn leadership information (Caust 2018). The job of the commercial center has gotten basic and has conjured a serious situation inside which colleges seem to be expanding comprehensively serious just as territorially delicate (Mahoney and Lim, 2015).

The basic of this issue are numerous and different. At one level, it has been an element of scholastic research that has tended to psychologize authority either as a psychological property of people or as a conduct idea preoccupied from the exact perception of its relevant conditions. For the vast majority of us, being available to obstruction is much the same as inviting a head cold. Be that as it may, it is one of life's Catch 22s that the occasions when we are generally anxious to push our own causes are the very occasions we should be the most responsive to counterarguments from individuals who are hesitant to see our perspective (Hansburg 2018).

All in all, accomplishment holes are not restricted to bring down financial or failing to meet expectations in school areas. Unexpectedly, a large number of the country's most noteworthy performing rural schools experience altogether lower school applications, higher dropout rates, and excessively low portrayal academic performance and praises level courses among their dark, Hispanic, and lower-salary understudies (Preis 2016).

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Reluctant leaders are as individual in their hesitance to learn as they are in their inspiration to learn; be that as it may, a few shared characteristics exist. One significant objective of teachers is to expand their understudies' autonomy and enthusiasm for learning. In spite of the fact that tokenism can be helpful to quickly snare hesitant students, instructors ought not to overlook the comprehensive view. In the event that educators anticipate that understudies should have a solid feeling of self-assurance toward the finish of each school year, they have to empower understudies' inborn inspiration during the whole school year. The accompanying proposals are expected to help this objective. In spite of the fact that they center on hesitant students, they can be adjusted to all students. Over the previous decades, instructor leadership contemplates have been led to research how educators see and practice educator initiative in various school settings, including youth training (Heikka et al., 2016). The arranged leadership in various ways, including formal, casual, and crossbreed, where half and half instructor leadership endeavors to keep up a viable harmony between formal or progressive force and casual or social force. Hunzicker (2017)

Late analyses on instructor leadership no longer endeavor to explore the administrative jobs or attributes of school leaders; rather, a few investigations have researched the educators' informal communities (Struyve 2014). The leadership is a territory where research is conceivable. It's additionally the expertise of a person with the assistance of which it's conceivable to lead or might be as it were to manage an individual, group, team, or an organization (Khan 2020).

Furthermore, the encounters and factors that ruined the way toward turning into a leader included disarray about one's position of leadership, exploring the center ground among partner and leader, and the absence of correspondence with the organization. The discoveries in this paper propose a few game-plans for supporting rising educator leaders. Educator leadership could likewise be upheld by having obvious sets of expectations just as being perceived somehow or another for satisfying that set of working responsibilities (Wenner and Campbell 2016).

In addition, imaginative work requires leadership that depends on impact, connections, and conveyed methods of working as opposed to conventional progressive authoritative methodologies dependent on force and authority. (Caust 2018). Although Empson (2014) thinks about hesitance in leadership in proficient assistance associations, featuring the logical and inspirational driving elements while distinguishing that now and again hesitance is claimed as opposed to really dependent on the craving to seem humble. The significance of social leadership has expanded given restored approach talk concerning the monetary commitment of expressions of the human experience and social part and spotlight on industry and authoritative endurance even with political, financial, and social assaults. Goodwin, K. (2020)

All in all, instructors were progressively situated towards understudy learning, however, lacking space was accessible for instituting educator leadership regarding instructor cooperation, shared administration, and intelligent practice. In this manner, suggestions for educator leadership improvement are talked about. Wan, W. P. E. (2020). Key components intervening the procedures of instructor leadership are summed up, including hierarchical societies (Kilinc, 2014). Yuen et al. (2018) found that the strengthening of instructor leadership in school-based educational plans can be authorized through a 'base up' approach – one that permits educators to practice prudence in making decisions in school-based educational plans utilizing an intelligent methodology that urges instructors to take activities in regular social communications. In which Confucian qualities, for example, enthusiasm connections despite everything win. In which junior educators act and react to such social standards by 'sparing appearances' and demonstrating admiration to seniors by counseling seniors, and in this way, the force elements may contort the 'equivalent' interest of instructors in dynamic (Yuen et al., 2015).

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This chapter provides information on the methodology of the study. This is a qualitative study and the name is “Reluctant to be educational leader”. A sample of only one school principle were drawn through a balanced outlined straightforward interview brings up that qualitative methodology and used semi-structured questionnaire for interview. This part presents the research design, target populace of the research, sample size, sampling technique, instruments, information gathering methodology, analysis of data, moral thought, and limitation of the research. The improvement of an exploration configuration follows coherently from the examination issue. This suggests the exploration issue coordinates the decision to plan. An examination configuration is characterized as "a lot of rules and guidelines to be followed intending to the exploration issue" (Mouton, 1996). This qualitative investigation was directed with semi-structured interviews with the private school's teacher in Kunar province. Information and individual encounters were acquired through the members' own words (Bogdan and Biklen, 1992) Sampling is a procedure of finding out about the public based on a sample drawn from it. An example is a subset of public units. The way toward testing comprises one component: Selecting the example; gathering the data, and making a derivation about the populace. Consumes and Groove, (2001), including that "examining includes choosing a gathering of individuals, occasions, practices or different components with which to lead an examination. "Populace alludes to all the components (people, items or substances) that meet certain criteria for incorporation in a given universe" (Bums and Grove, 2005). They further demonstrate that the meaning of the populace relies upon the example criteria and the closeness of members in different settings. Depict the arrangement of the populace (N) in your investigation. At that point proceed with a depiction of the example and examining method. As indicated by this strategy, which has a place with the class of non-likelihood inspecting procedures, test individuals are chosen based on their insight, connections, and mastery in regards to an examination subject. The fundamental reason for the exploration was to investigate sees the Reluctant to be educational leader of the principle of the school in Johor state, Malesia. This was finished by endeavoring to respond to the accompanying research questions:

- A. How they perceived the post of principal/dean of their organization/school?
- B. What are their perceptions for those who interested to be the principal/dean of their educational organizations?
- C. Does the leadership post symbolize the highest achievement of being a teacher/lecturer? If nope, why?
- D. Does the appointment will reflect their promotion? If yes, why. If no, why?
- E. Why some middle layer leaders (senior assistant/head of department) are not interested to be principal/ dean of their organization?
- F. Based on their perceptions what are four major reasons used to reject the post of dean/principal besides their high passion in teaching?
- G. What suggestions and recommendations can be forwarded for those who not interested to be principal/dean but thinking of having their promotions?

IV. PARTICIPANT

The main interviewee was the principle of school in Johor, Malaysia. With a solid corporate, a compact all-inclusive nearness, and an amazing scholastic continue, and strong corporate establishment, strong overall proximity, and an extraordinary academic resume. The whole meeting was held in the workplaces of the particular interviewees. The meeting permitted people to share their comprehension with respect to authority, preparing, and worth was as a head of the department. Mugenda and Mugenda (1999)

noticed that the objective populace is a populace to which the specialist needed to sum up the consequences of the investigation. Right now, the target populace for this examination will include one principle schools in Johor, Malaysia. The aim of this study to use such a population was to obtain data that enables the researcher to understand principle“ Reluctant to be educational leader “.

V. DATA COLLECTION

The sole wellspring of information, which was the essential source naturally, was the subjects of concern the school’s principle of Johore Bahro state. Expected information was gathered by method for semi-structured questionnaire interview to the said member was utilized to collect qualitative information from the respondents. Field notes with portrayals, direct references, and spectator comments were recorded not long after the recognitions (Merriam, 1998). Given the researchers foundation it was simple for her to relate to the members' reactions in spite of the fact that she made preparations for forcing her own view on the members. The social area of the specialist and the members as far as their race, sexual orientation, the societal position assumed a critical job in molding the examination procedure (Edwards, 1990; Orbele, 2002). A meeting was upheld with an examination of chronicles containing a discourse and an open chat on subjects of pre and post-getting ready of the leader of the division. The talks were also recorded with approval from the leader of the office. Consequently, the expert pulled around her journal and recorded her observations at the most punctual open door after a discernment.

VI. DATA ANALYSIS

As to the investigation of information, the researcher applied a semi-structured questionnaire interview, to be specific, to dissect the accumulated information. With this interview, the researcher utilized qualitative information, was applied in breaking down information on interview questions and things under research goals where the connection information of reluctant leader was placed into account.

This interview was semi-structured and sound recorded, recorded accurate and one member was the school’s principle of Johore Bahro state Malaysia. An outline was sent to the participants for respondent confirmation, the member checked this rundown. The Analysis began straightforwardly after the meeting and proceeded at the same time with information collection. The subjects picked for our meetings dependent on the unique authority preparing when became principle and reluctant leader for before and after appointing the principle, whereby the ideas of occupation assets, work requests, and job communication were at first viewed as primary topics. Related watchwords for an asset could show positive feelings or articulations, related catchwords for request could demonstrate negative feelings or articulations. We likewise made notes if such remarks were made according to one job or if these influenced different jobs. One citation could contain different codes. During the examination, codes and results were talked about among different creators consistently to additionally refine coding and think about rising topics. We again surveyed our codes utilizing work commitment writing and chose to include as sharpening ideas execution input and assets and requests on an individual level as a sharpening idea. All the more explicitly, we remembered for the layout whether an asset or request was owing to the work or the member, utilizing indistinguishable watchwords from previously. Now, the codes stayed unaltered yet an elective course of action of subjects was picked to wager after every update of the topics and codes, all past interview was returned to and broke down with the new coding structure.

VII. IDENTIFIED THEMES

The findings of the case study provide an explanation of the events that occurred in depth (Yin, 1994). Information obtained from the interviews found that the informants had responded to the answers which provided a detailed description of his experience in school leadership. Based on the information obtained through the interview process informants provide data as a guide for analysis.

VIII. ORGANIZATION SOCIALISATION

The findings show that informants practice organizational socialization leadership throughout their service in education. This is based on the results of the interviews that have been conducted.

“And in June 2004 I received an administrative transfer request at the Curriculum Center, Human Resource Development Sector of the Johor State Education Department before transferring to the Curriculum Unit in the same sector in 2013.”

The results of the interviews revealed that the informants were appointed Supervisors of the Johor State Department of Education at a young age based on their experience as a regular teacher who was active in the curriculum before being appointed a Senior Assistant Teacher of Student Affairs. Based on the Mannen and Scheins (1979) Socialization Tactics Tactics, this Senior Assistant Teacher of Student Affairs has individual characteristics in which informants have transformed themselves and adapted to the organizational environment.

IX. POSITIVE RESPONSES AND EXPECTATIONS

Interviews were conducted also answered questions concerning his responses and expectations of the highest posts in either school teachers and principals. This further reinforces that informants practice leadership in socializing organizations. And give support and respect to colleagues who carry out their duties as Headmaster or Principal.

“Rationally, I respect and admire any colleagues who carry out their duties and roles as Headmaster or Principal. This is because I personally feel not quite ready for that direction even those who feel I have already experienced and qualified to fill such posts.”

The educational experience various changes in line with current developments. Therefore, either the Headmaster or the Principal also plays a role in keeping with the current development of education. It is sometimes difficult to assimilate these changes according to their respective interpretations. This is because every school environment has different levels of ability, speciality, student privilege and family background. As headmasters and principals, consideration and ability to govern according to existing guidelines and adapted to the advantages and strengths of people and their environment is necessary in order to form a positive mold culture of the school.

X. MOTIVATION SUPPORT COLLEAGUES

The respondents gave the answer that is motivated to provide feedback related to the question asked about their perception of his fellow teachers who are interested in becoming headmaster or principal, including among more junior in terms of seniority of service.

“I welcome their passion and requirements. To be honest, I fully support any colleague who wants to go higher. As I mentioned earlier, education is transformative and its development needs to be able to be absorbed by every layer of school leaders and school administration lineup.”

Any teacher who is prepared and willing to take on the role of top administrator in the school must have thought and reasoned about the challenges and responsibilities they would be facing. So do the junior teachers in the service. Each individual has its own advantages and leadership style. Each of these advantages is a plus minus for them. They have a high degree of competitiveness to meet the challenges of current education management. Besides being exposed to the application of technology in current education.

However, it is common knowledge that there are many factors such as the increase in Grade in the short term in which teachers who hold the Headmaster with Grade DG42 are allowed to apply for the DG44 fast track increase after serving at least 4 years or more. Before that they have to go through the National Professional Qualification for Educational Leaders (NPQEL)) includes an interview prior application and a fitness test.

XI. DEVELOPMENTS AND VARIATIONS IN SERVICES

Respondents described that trusting as a Headmaster or Principal was not the culmination of a teacher's performance and achievement in his service as emphasized in the Malaysian Education Development Plan from 2013 to 2025 (Ministry of Education Malaysia, 2013).

“It depends on the specific situation, the point of view of the individual, the demands of the current needs and the attractive factors that promise a particular increase. From my point of view, holding the highest level of trust in the school either as the Headmaster or the Principal does not represent the highest achievement as the teacher.”

With that, the headmaster or principal role is to comply with their functions transformational leadership (James & Balasandran 2013; Rahimi & Yusri, 2014; Yusri & Aziz, 2015, 2014) to develop school goals of the curriculum, co-curricular, social and emotional development of students. The challenge of teachers is increasing with the current education. The diversity of

fields and teacher involvement can contribute to the changing nature of education in general. Satisfaction working in education is not just to achieve high positions in education itself, but to the extent that we can contribute to our respective areas of expertise and ability. What is important about each of these initiatives and efforts is towards the development of a balanced student-centered process as a product of human capital from the educational realm itself.

Student engagement whether in or out of the classroom is a real reinforcement and experience of students as part of the process of human development in life. The involvement of students, whether through teaching and learning, extra-curricular activities and social relationships with the school community and the local community will provide valuable input for them. It is not the highlight but part of the diversity of experience, knowledge, memory, skills and technical strengths and challenges throughout their service.

XII. REALITY OF APPOINTMENT AND PROMOTION

Generally the appointment of Headmaster or Principal is classified as promotion without any increase in Grade of Service (Service Circular Letter Number 10 2017).. The appointment to the post is among tribute to teachers on their performance and efforts that have been undertaken and produced results so far. In addition, it also ranks among the methods of appreciation for teachers who are committed, experienced and have the ability to serve and involve themselves to higher administration and management.

However, they have to apply for the Program of the National Professional Qualification for Educational Leaders (National Professional Qualification for Educational Leaders (NPQEL)). After completing the documentation and information online, any teacher who has passed the initial qualification screening process will undergo the qualification process prior interview.. If they get past the interview process, they will have to undergo and pass Fitness Test. When the applicant has passed both, and then they will be included in the list of applications for the current year to undergo a preparatory course NPQEL for 3 months.

XIII. CAREER DEVELOPMENT AND ITS INFLUENCE

Respondent shared his experience of 20 years and 15 years working as a Supervisor in the Johor State Department of Education when asked about why some leaders of the middle layer is not interested in becoming a Headmaster or Principal. Self-concept changes over time and develops as a result of experience. As such, career development is lifelong (Donald E. Super, 1994). He who has previously served at the highest level of management has given different dimensions of perspective to the matter.

“The various fields of work, especially involving the management and implementation of state-level programs for Johor education citizen, including implementing education programs at the national level, the participation of national programs and initiatives require the participation of international program requires willingness mental, physical, commitment and sacrifice.”

Relocation to school has given the space to organize current changes. Although various proposals and views that suggested applying for the National Professional Qualification for Educational Leaders (NPQEL) to allow him to continue to the next level, he can only state that he in term preparing himself.

XIV. GOALS AND FUTURE ACHIEVEMENTS BESIDES TEACHING

Respondents gave the following justifications when asked four main reasons used to reject the post of Headmaster besides their high interest in teaching. Firstly, respondent needed to create self-preparation before a tendency to carry out the mandate as headmaster. As we was told, the respondent had just returned to school after serving 15 years in the Johor State Education Department, besides to adapt the changes in the current state of education in schools. Secondly, as reinforcing the above, respondent currently pursuing postgraduate studies in Management and Administration at the Faculty of Social Sciences and Society at Universiti Teknologi Malaysia so that the knowledge gained will be useful in the future..

Thirdly, respondents who are now 44 years of age have 15 years of service before compulsory retirement at age 60. And was initially involved with the top management at a young age in the Johor State Department of Education involving the co-curricular management of Johor, made him want to explore the field of job position as Senior Assistant Teacher of Student Affairs for a specific period of time. Fourth, the respondent wants to focus on his current studies at Universiti Teknologi Malaysia, spending quality time with his family well as majoring the main task of my current job spec in school.. The Covid-19 Movement Control Command provides valuable wisdom as it enables quality time with the family.

Suggestions

Respondents provided suggestions and recommendations based on the point of view, experience of the Senior Headmaster and Principal including reading information for reference can be made for those who are not interested in becoming a Headmaster or Principal but are considering applying for a promotion. Firstly, fellow teachers who are interested in the proper mental and physical health. The variety of duties that require sacrifice and commitment to provide for the administration of a school in order to follow existing guidelines while dealing with a variety of human resources. Because of that, there is the National Professional Qualification for Educational Leaders (NPQEL) as mandatory requirements to be settled first. Secondly, the teachers need to know and understand the duties colleagues at school. Middle School Leaders include Senior Administrative Assistant Teachers, Senior Student Affairs Teachers, Curriculum Senior Assistant Teachers and Evening Supervisors, with roles, functions and complement each other. The role of the headmaster is comprised entirely administration and management. Thirdly, teachers also need to learn to understand school financial management including cash management, payment vouchers, check-out and cancellation arrangements, Per capita Grants Assistance Fractions, SUWA (Public Money Contribution) and so on. Each has guidelines and is referenced along with the Financial Circular Letter effective during the year which is accessible through the website of the State Accountants Department, State Audit Department, State Education Department and Ministry of Education Malaysia.

Fourth, in addition, teachers should also be aware of Procurement and Assets as well as related procedures and management. Issues often arise in relation to records and dispositions even when the buying procedure is done correctly. Management is often overlooked but can have implications in the future such as student accidents involving assets that should have been eliminated and so on. Fifth, it will be directly related to File Management. Most schools have a School File List which can be downloaded through the State Education Department and the National Archives Department and customized to the School Quality Management System (SPSK). Besides, we should be parallel with the needs and File Management SKPMg2 justification and supporting evidence.

Sixth, teachers also need to be prepared for changes in national education whether they include long-term education development plans such as the Education Development Plan 2013 - 2025 as well as current education programs such as the High Immersive Program. In addition, there are numerous references to existing implementation guidelines through either the Circular Letter (SPI) or Post Letter (Notification Letter) by the Ministry of Education Malaysia, General Circular issued by the Prime Minister's Department or the Secretary of State or the Financial Circular (SPK) by The National Audit Department or the Accountant General's Department.

XV. LIMITATION

There were several limitation that have to be pointed out. Firstly, our findings and results were based on the analysis of interview. The respective person that we interviewed was a senior assistance teacher from one of the school in Johor Bahru. He has various experiences of his management skill in school. In addition, he had a 15 years of previous experiences in Johor State Education Department. We felt blessed as we can interview to him who was full of knowledge and wonderful experiences. However, we found this data was not enough for us to do the analysis. As everyone has their own perception in management skill, so there will be different traits of leadership by themselves. For instance, we need to refer and seek for other leader of their opinion for school management.

Furthermore, we faced a world COVID-19 pandemic in this year. Minister of Malaysia took action immediately and created Movement Control Order (MCO) to prevent people to get off this kind of virus. So, everyone was not allowed to come out for group meeting. This was a big problem for us because we can't go to library to borrow the book and access more information over there. In addition, it's a hard and tough time to every students for discussion of face by face. Hence, people need to use phone to call or video call to each member for further discussion. This will use a lot of money to buy the data and pay for the calling bills.

Moreover, we also faced there lack of connection in our home area. Connection of internet was weak and not stable all the time. This is another challenge for us to access the information from the internet. This assignment need to acquire one of the senior assistance teacher for having interview. Since there was impossible to meet each other for interview. Then we planned for interviewing by using Google Meeting. Due of lack of connection, we faced a lot of problem by reconnecting the line in this interview.

XVI. DISCUSSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Based on the findings, we found that the most challenge of senior assistance teacher don't go further for applying to an educational leader is they can't select a workplace after graduating to be a principal. For instance, most of senior assistance teacher having a wonderful family in their life. They were worried to transfer to a new school where they have to separate with family. It is because all the decision will make by the supervisor from Johor State Educational Department. So we suggested to the educational leader as take this matter as a challenge in their life. After being at a new school of 2 years, they might transfer to their city if there have a post for them. We can take this challenging moment as we can make ourselves getting stronger to become a professional and effective leader.

By reading our study, educational leader can well in understanding the perception of management skills in school. Teachers also can apply numerous of alternative way to become educational leader instead of to be principal in school. We stated there are variety of promotion for middle layer leaders to accomplish their post in organization. Based on findings and data, we can give a clear and distinct conceptual to the leader who wants to access the higher post in organization.

This study "Reluctant to be educational leader" should also be available at the research center for future development by research and for related literature. The potential and usefulness of our analysis of findings and data cannot be overemphasized, we suggested to make it more available to the public research for further clear and detail conceptual of this study. This is how far we cherished of the data outcome. In future, teacher or leader can based on this study as a guideline to motivate them to be a good educational leader. Our group recommended the following recommendations:

- 1) Based on discussion and analysis it is recommended.
- 2) Head of the educational institute must have a skill that how to communicate.
- 3) Head of the educational institute must not be static.
- 4) Role of the head of educational institute has to be dynamic.
- 5) Leader of the institute must possess the capability to treat any type of situation.
- 6) Leader of the educational institute must have the capability to update him-self academically, administratively to cope with the problems, and to take the team in a right direction.
- 7) Leader of the educational institute must have the capability to resolve the conflict when arise in the institute.
- 8) Principal of the educational institute have to praise their staff to generate better results.
- 9) There must be proper training programs from the leader for their subordinate to meet with the challenges of modern age.
- 10) Top leaders must have a vision, which guide the department in a right direction.
- 11) There must be coordination among the team members and leadership to avoid miss understanding and conflicts.

XVII. FINDINGS

Findings are separated into two sections that address the two research questions. First, evidence is presented demonstrating leadership reluctance across several arts and cultural disciplines. Their community often recognizes this leadership reluctance. Second, antecedent factors are described for reasons behind leadership reluctance. Finally, implications for the arts and cultural sector are discussed.

XVIII. CONCLUSION

Based on the research findings on professional work and leadership challenge, senior assistance teacher in the school has to focus primarily on accountability, audit, inspection and control. However, formal control fail to engage professional in ways that enroll their commitment and willingness. For example, transformational leader can be accomplished and recognized formally the values and ethnics of shared leadership (Pearce Conger, 2013) rather than to remain trapped in practices that reflect and reinforce heroic conceptions of leadership. We can clearly see that the plugging of gap mentality and the expectations of working resembles some of this demand on the goodwill of educational leader to deliver well in excess of their statutory obligations and the system of formal rewards.

In addition, we still can see that some of senior assistance teachers seeking promotion especially when it involves a threat to their pedagogic values, work-life balance, or involves their reputation. At the same time, they do develop alternative conceptions of leadership that refuse the implication of sacrificing life to work (Bathmaker, 2006). However, there also have some senior

assistance teachers unwilling to be educational leader. They have to face a lot of difficulties and problems at their workplace. Teachers who always against them can be slightly demotivate them in order to accomplish and achieve their goals at school.

In conclusion, educational leader do not necessarily see themselves as leaders but as professionals (Collinson, 2003). The educational leader must has an influential role in inspiring, motivating, affirming and also challenging or extending the practice and pedagogy of educators. It is a joint endeavor involving inquiry and reflection, which can significantly impact on the important work educators do with children and families. With the role's introduction, a number of myths have emerged about its responsibilities. One of these is that educational leader must complete all of the programming for all educators. This is a narrow and potentially limiting view of this study.

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